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The Nutritional Value of Cowpeas and Cowpeas-Based Rabbit Weaner Diets

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Abstract

The study sought to determine the nutritional composition of cowpeas and the subsequent formulated *Chinchilla gigantea* rabbit weaner cowpeas-based diets. Three samples of CBC3 variety of cowpea and twelve sub-samples of formulated diets (four per diet) were subjected to a proximate analysis to determine their nutritional composition. Proximate analysis results showed that cowpeas contain 93.3% Dry matter, 21.44% crude protein, metabolizable energy of 3290.25kcal/kg, 4.24% crude fibre and 2.05% ether extracts. Three diets were then formulated comprising of 0% cowpeas (control diet), 25% cowpeas and 30% cowpeas. Statistical analysis of the nutritional levels of the sub-samples indicated that the three diets were not significant in terms of dry matter, metabolizable energy, crude protein, ether extracts, crude fibre and phosphorus ($p>0.05$). Diet three had lower calcium content than the other diets ($P<0.05$). Diet one had calcium content of 1.51%, diet two had 1.60% while diet three had 0.925%. All the diets contained the same nutritional parameters for the main nutrients with all the nutrients meeting the requirements of the rabbits.

Keywords: Anti-nutritional Factors, Cowpeas, Diet, Nutritional Composition, Rabbit weaners.

Introduction

Feed is the most limiting factor in the Zimbabwean small scale rabbit production sector (Gono *et al*, (2013). In general feed costs account up to 70% of the total costs of production (Rauw and Gomez-Raya, 2015). Energy ingredients constitute up to 60% of the total diet components whilst protein ingredients take up to 40%, Mpofu, (2005). In terms of cost, energy ingredients account up to 40% of the total cost of the diet, Igwebuike *et al*, (2013) while protein ingredients account up to 55% of the total feed cost especially soya beans (Richard and Nigel, 2018). Protein cost and availability is thus a major concern at a global level. In Zimbabwe, the issue of feed shortage in the rabbit enterprise is an area of concern as witnessed by unavailability of rabbit feed on the market and from major feed firms. Currently major suppliers are National Foods and Capital Foods private limited companies. This calls for the need to consider various alternative non-conventional protein sources to improve on small stock livestock productivity especially rabbits.

Feed intake and utilization by animals is depended on a number of factors ranging from its energy level (Maertens and Gidenne, 2016) and protein level (Matondi *et al*, 2015). It is therefore important to balance the nutrients that might affect acceptability of feed by the rabbits especially these two. Balancing of the nutrients for feed formulation can only be achieved if the nutritive values of the feed ingredients are known (Mpofu, 2005). To this cause, proximate analysis of the main feed ingredients should be done as composition for the same ingredients can be affected by a number of factors. Anti-nutritional factors determination and pre-treatment is also critical (Yacout, 2016) as this gives an insight in terms of permissible inclusion levels. Feed composition should be adequate to address the nutritional requirements of the rabbits so that productivity is not

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compromised (Halls, 2010).

Materials and Methods

Experimental Diets

Three (3) iso-nitrogenous and iso-energetic rabbit weaner diets were formulated and compounded. The diets comprised of maize, soya bean meal (control diet), mineral supplements and graded levels of cowpeas for the diets where soya bean meal was to be partially replaced by cowpeas. The diets were as follows; 0% cowpeas (control diet), 25% cowpeas and 30% cowpeas inclusion level. No direct roughage was added into the diets since hay was fed at *ad libitum*. CBC3 variety of cowpeas was used for feed formulation. It was firstly roasted as a pre-treatment measure to deal with anti-nutritional factors. Matondi *et al*, (2015) used dehulled- fermented cowpeas. Dehulling is however not a common practice and is not easy to follow for most farmers due lack of dehulling facilities. The most common method of dealing with anti-nutritional factors is roasting, thus the same method was used in this study.

Proximate Analysis and Feed Formulation

Before diet formulation, maize, soya meal and cowpeas were subjected to an assessment of dry matter, crude protein, ether extract, crude fibre, calcium and phosphorus using the Association of Official Agricultural Chemists (AOAC), (2003) procedures, Plate 5.0-7.0. Formulation of diets was done using Feedwin® Interactive version 1.01 computer package and also verified using Dlpd.htm.xls by Mpofu, (2005) following the feed composition recommendations by Halls, (2010) for proteins, energy and fat. For energy the formulation was guided by Shaahu *et al*, (2014) and Abubakar *et al* (2006). For the other key nutrients (crude fibre, calcium and phosphorous), general local rabbit feed standards from feed manufactures were used, Capital Foods Pvt Ltd (Plate 3.0) and National Foods Pvt Ltd (Plate 4.0). All the ingredients were milled to mash form and mixed into a ration. Limestone flour and mono-calcium phosphate were used as chief sources of calcium and phosphorous respectively. The three diets were thus formulated to meet the highlighted standards, ME kcal/kg (+-3000.00), CP (18%), CF (8%), Fat (5%), Ca (0.9%) and P (0.6%).

Ingredients and Formulated Diets Data Collection

Data on the nutritional values from proximate analysis results of each of the ingredients three sub-samples was collected and average nutritional value determined. For the diets sub-samples nutritional data for each of the sub-sample was computed for subsequent statistical analysis.

Formulated Diets

Table 1.0: *Composition and Cost of Formulated Diets*

Ingredients %	Diet		
	Control (0% Cowpeas)	25% Cowpeas	30% (Cowpeas)
Maize	63.73	49.48	46.66
Soya bean meal	34.13	23.20	21.00
Cowpeas	0.00	25.00	30.00
Mono Calcium Phosphate (MCP)	1.11	1.15	1.15
Limestone flour	0.93	1.07	1.05
Salt	0.10	0.10	0.10
Total Mix	100.00	100.00	100.00
Cost (US\$/100kg)	45.18	43.19	42.79

Description of the area

The experiment was carried out at Henderson Research Institute. It is located south of the Equator in the Southern hemisphere of Africa. The Institute lies at 17°35' latitudinally and 30°58' longitudinally. The Institute receives a Savannah type of climate. According to agro-potential zonation system, the Institute is in natural

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farming region IIa in Mazowe District of Mashonaland Central Province of Zimbabwe. Henderson Research Institute stretches from the 28th km peg to the 35th km peg north of capital Harare, along the Harare – Bindura highway. The institute is located at an altitude of 1,300 meters above sea level. In fact, the place lies in a valley. Total annual rainfall ranges between 750 mm to 1,000 mm. The rainfall is usually received from mid-November to mid-April with mid-season droughts experienced in January. Although the place receives high rainfall amount temperature patterns resemble those of low agricultural potential with wide temperature range. In such areas major farming activities include production of drought resistant crops and livestock. Average temperatures range from 15^oC to 22^oC with lowest winter temperatures going as low as 0^oC in July whilst highest temperatures can go up to 35^oC in October.

Research Design

A completely randomised design was used for samples of feed following procedures by Muriu *et al*, (2002), experimental model, $Y_i = \mu + T_i + E_i$, where Y_i was the total nutrient content observed, μ was the overall mean nutrient content, T_i was the diet effect on the nutrient in question and E_i was the random error term on nutrient level.

Sampling Procedure

Feed ingredients and diets samples were randomly taken throughout the whole lot using a cup. A sample was taken from each ingredient. For proximate analysis purposes each sample was sub-divided into three sub-samples then the average nutrient level from the three sub-samples for each ingredient was calculated after the sub-samples were subjected to a proximate analysis following the AOAC, (2003) procedure. For the diets, four samples from each diet were sent for proximate analysis to determine the nutrient levels. Each sample was further portioned into three sub-samples which were then subjected to a proximate analysis following the same AOAC, (2003) procedure.

Data Collection Procedure

Data on the nutritional values from proximate analysis results of each of the ingredients three sub-samples was collected and average nutritional value determined. For the diets sub-samples nutritional data for each of the sub-sample was computed for subsequent statistical analysis.

Data Analysis Procedure

Nutritional parameters proximate analysis results of the twelve sub-samples, four from each diet were subjected to an independent sample Kruskal-Wallis probability distribution test to determine whether the diets had similar nutritional attributes using IBM SPSS Statistics 20.

RESULTS

Nutritional Composition of Ingredients

Proximate analysis results showed that cowpeas used in this study had crude protein content of 21.44% and 3290.25 kcal per kilogram of metabolizable energy. Soya meal had 40.5% crude protein and energy level of 3243.55 kcal/ kg. The nutritional composition results of other nutrients of interest are as indicated, Table 2.0. Results also showed that the main energy source, maize, had crude protein content of 6.56% and metabolizable energy of 3006.30 kcal per kilogram.

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Table 2.0: Proximate Analysis Results of Ingredients

Ingredient	DM	ME Kcal/Kg	CP (%)	EE (%)	CF (%)	Ca (%)	P (%)
Cowpeas (Roasted)	93.3	3290.25	21.44	2.05	4.24	0.15	0.35
Maize	89.84	3006.30	6.56	5.00	1.43	0.4	0.25
Soya beans	91.2	3243.55	40.5	2.7	5.65	0.33	0.57

Nutritional Composition of the Calculated Diets

The calculated diets had similar nutritive attributes, except for Ether Extracts (EE) and Crude Fibre (CF), Table 3.0. EE followed an inverse relationship with cowpea inclusion level whilst CF followed a proportional relationship with cowpeas inclusion level. Cowpeas had the highest Dry Matter (DM) content, Table 2.0. Its high inclusion rate was associated with less maize and soya, thus DM was bound to increase as cowpea was increased. The same was the case with the trend of maize in relation to cowpeas inclusion rate. From this study, DM content increased with more cowpeas inclusion level, Table 3.0.

Table 3.0: Calculated Nutritional Composition of Diets

Nutrient	Requirements	Diet 1 Control (0% Cowpeas)	Diet 2 25% Cowpeas	Diet 3 30% (Cowpeas)
% DM	-	90.46	91.19	91.34
Metabolizable Energy (ME-kcal/kg)	2700-3500	3022.94	3062.58	3070.96
% CP	16-20	18.00	18.00	18.00
% EE	5.00	4.11	3.61	3.52
% CF	8.00	2.85	3.08	3.13
% Ca	0.90	0.90	0.90	0.90
% P	0.60	0.60	0.60	0.60
Cost (US\$/100kg)		45.18	43.19	42.79

Feedwin® Interactive version 1.01

Proximate Analysis Results of Calculated Diets Samples

Independent samples Kruskal-Wallis probability distribution test for the proximate analysis results of the calculated diets samples showed that there were no significant differences for DM, Metabolizable Energy (ME), Crude Protein (CP), CF, EE and Phosphorous (P) content across the three treatment diets ($p > 0.05$). DM content for the diets ranged from 90.375% to 90.463% with a grand mean of 90.429. ME ranged from 3022.94 kcal/kg to 3070.96 kcal/kg across diet one to three with a grand mean of 3038. Numerically, both DM and ME followed a proportional relationship with the percentage inclusion rate of cowpeas. CP ranged between 22.48 and 20.29% across diet one to three with a grand mean of 21.49%. CP followed an inverse relationship with cowpeas inclusion level. Diet three had significantly lower calcium content than the other two as it was generally inversely related to cowpeas inclusion level ($p < 0.05$). Calcium content was 1.51%, 1.6% and 0.925% for diet one, two and three respectively. Results of the analysis of all the nutrients showed that they met the nutritional requirements of rabbit weaner growers, Table 3.0.

Table 4.0: Proximate Analysis Results of the Diets

Parameter	Diet 1 (Control)	Diet 2 (25% Cowpeas)	Diet 3 (30% Cowpeas)	Grand Mean	P-Value	Sign
Samples	4	4	4	-	-	-
% DM	90.38	90.45	90.463	90.43	0.938	NS
ME (Kcal/kg)	3006	3028	3080	3038	0.174	NS
% CP	22.48	21.71	20.29	21.49	0.254	NS
% EE	4.06	3.76	2.65	3.49	0.058	NS
% CF	2.86	3.34	3.17	3.16	0.442	NS
% Ca	1.51 ^b	1.6 ^b	0.93 ^a	1.35	0.013	*
% P	0.67	0.66	0.64	0.66	0.912	NS

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SEM – Standard Error of Mean

^{ab} – Mean values with the same or without superscript in the same row do not differ ($p>0.05$)

* Significantly different

NS Not significant

DISCUSSION**Nutritional Composition of Ingredients**

The nutritional value of cowpeas obtained from the analysis is in agreement with studies by other scientists (Ikhlas and Sirelkhatim, (2016) who reported that cowpeas contain 18 – 35% CP. However, protein content of the cowpeas in this study was relatively low. (Kamboj and Nanda, (2017) established that cowpeas contain 25% CP whilst Matondi *et al*, (2015) noted 26.09% CP. The low protein level observed from this study might have arisen from varietal differences and agronomic management of the crop, especially soil fertility management as highlighted by Adino *et al*, (2018) who attributed the same scenario to fertilizer levels. The same author also highlighted that efficiency of treatment method done to cowpeas cannot be overlooked. This might have also applied for the CP content level of the maize used in the study which was lower when compared to the general protein content of white maize and that observed by Adino *et al*, (2018). The observations on cowpeas CF, Lipids, calcium and phosphorus were in line with those of Kamboj and Nanda, (2017). Energy level observed from the diets in this study was high due to a high energy content of whole cowpeas, maize and soya meal. These observation were however contrary to those by Matondi *et al*, (2015) who observed a low energy level possibly because of reduced CF of cowpeas as a result of decorticating.

The nutritional composition results of soya meal from the analysis results of this study showed some marked variance for CP, CF and EE against observations by Hassan, (2013) for the same solvent extracted soya meal. This can also be attributed to varietal differences, agronomic management and extend of oil expression. Figures from this study were 40.5%, 5.65% and 2.7% while Hassan, (2013) sighted 44%, 7% and 0.8% respectively. Calcium and phosphorus were almost in the same range of 0.33% and 0.57% compared to 0.29 % and 0.65% of Hassan, (2013) respectively. According to Hassan, (2013) the equivalence of toasted cowpeas, heat treated soya bean, contains 37% CP, 5.5% CF, 18% fat, 0.25% Ca and 0.58% P. The major differences are notable for crude protein and fat. Analysis results from this study were not in congruence with the work by Adino *et al*, (2018) for Soya meal, cowpeas and maize, especially for the key nutrients. The same reasons could be explanatory to these variances.

Nutritional Composition of the Calculated Diets

Protein level of the diets in this study was high due to high inclusion rate of the protein ingredients, Table 1. The proportional increase in CF content as the level of cowpeas inclusion was increased is mostly attributable to a low proportion of maize in the diet as more cowpeas (which contained more CF) had an effect of reducing proportion of maize. The gradual decrease in EE as cowpeas level increase was attributed to a high level of EE in maize. More cowpeas in the diets resulted in less maize. Since higher inclusion levels of cowpeas was associated with reduction of maize, EE was also bound to fall since maize contains a high level of it. The same pattern for CF was also observed by Matondi *et al*, (2015) in their study. The inclusion rate of maize was also decreasing with more cowpeas inclusion level in their diets except for the 10% cowpeas diet where maize inclusion level was very high. This was mainly attributed to the high energy level in cowpeas. EE trend of the diets of this study closely followed those of (Adino *et al*, 2018).

CF was however not in congruent, instead of the increasing trend observed from this study, Adino *et al*, (2018) observed a decreasing trend. This is possibly because of the decreasing trend of soya beans with more cowpeas inclusion rate since the crude fibre of soya beans used in their study had very high CF content compared to that

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used in this study. The trend of maize inclusion level with more cowpeas inclusion in this study was also not in congruent with (Adino *et al*, 2018). This is attributable to the high energy level of soya beans used in their study and this high energy has a reduction effect on maize inclusion.

Proximate Analysis Results of Calculated Diets Samples

Compared to other scientists' cowpea based rabbit diets, the proximate results of this study showed a marked difference on the nutritional composition. This study established 21.49% CP, 3.49% EE and 3.16% CF against the 46.3% CP, 1.2% EE and 62.1% CF diets by Mohammed and Jamala, (2013). Diets by Matondi *et al*, (2015) had a range of 640 to 1348 kcal/kg energy, 10.21 to 20.36% CP and 3.1 to 3.6% CF compared to the 3006 to 3080 kcal/kg energy, 20.29 to 22.48% CP and 2.86 to 3.17% CF of this study. Results of this study are in agreement with Shaahu *et al*, (2014) in their study on lablab as protein source in rabbits for the energy level of the diets, however nutritional components showed marked differences. Nutritive levels from this study are not comparable to the (24.75 to 34.33% CP), (2.52 to 9.85% CF) and (47.81 to 60.45% EE) by Shaahu *et al*, (2014). Results from this study established that most nutrients in the final diets fell at or slightly above the calculated diets showing that the formulation softwares used are reliable.

Conclusion

Results from this study established that roasted CBC3 cowpeas contain 93.3% DM, 3290.25 kcal/kg energy, 21.44% CP, 2.05% EE, 4.24 CF, 0.15% Ca and 0.35% P. CBC3 cowpeas contains relatively low crude protein. Variety and agronomic management of the cowpea determines its nutritional value. Decorticated cowpeas have high energy levels. Higher inclusion levels of cowpeas have a cost reduction effect on the diet. Feed formulation softwares are generally reliable, all the nutrients in the formulated diets met the recommended nutritional levels. The diets were iso-nitrogenous and iso-energetic.

Recommendations

Although CBC3 cowpeas contain relatively low crude protein, farmers can use it as a blend with conventional protein sources in order to achieve the desired nutrient levels of formulated diets. Use of it will reduce cost of the feed. Cowpeas, just like any other legume requires pre-treatment in order to reduce the effect of anti-nutritional factors. In diet formulations, it is important that diets are iso-energetic and iso-nitrogenous, hence the need to embrace feed formulation softwares should be of particular emphasis. In feed formulation softwares are instrumental for accurate feed formulation results. Further studies on isolation of cowpeas anti-nutritional factors can be done as a way of validating this work.

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